

With and Within

The Collaborative Practice of Kura Workshop

Niklas Fanelso

Technical University of Munich

Introduction

KURA is a process-oriented project to retrofit a monument protected barn in the village of Gerswalde into our architecture workshop, applying the Design Science Research methodology. The aim is the holistic transformation of the building, by exclusively using ecological building materials and reclaimed building elements sourced from the local region, facilitated through a collaborative process with local craftspeople to strengthen community ties and promote regional craftsmanship.

By directly relating the design on the real artefact—the building itself—rather than using meta-artefacts like models and plans, the project fosters a practical, hands-on approach to architectural design and construction. The design system combines bio-based and geo-based materials with a holistic social practice, enabling regenerative architectural practices, enhanced regional architectural culture, and the revitalisation of rural communities, that can guide similar projects in different cultural and regional contexts.

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Exterior view showing the monumented protected ensemble in the village center with the workshop building on the left side. Image: Zara Pfeifer, 2023

Interior showing the ground floor of the workshop with a floor sunflower-oil pigmented lime screed on an insulation made from recycled glass. Image: Zara Pfeifer, 2023

Methodology

In the field of architecture, it is crucial to differentiate between meta-artefacts and real artefacts. Architects often communicate through abstractions like models and plans, which serve as meta-artefacts. These meta-artefacts are not the actual building, but represent and refer to them. An architectural drawing can be considered a real artefact if it is viewed as an independent work on its own. The KURA project emphasizes direct engagement with the building itself as the primary ‘real artefact,’ minimizing reliance on conventional meta-artefacts. This approach enabled adaptive, hands-on problem-solving that responded dynamically to the building’s structural and material needs, fostering a more grounded and immediate design practice. The Design Science Research (DSR) methodology (Hevner, 2007) originated from business informatics, but is highly applicable to architectural design. It is structured around three cycles. The design cycle, facilitated on-site material testing and real-time adjustments of artefacts. This iterative cycle is familiar to most architects as it involves continuous evaluation and improvement. The relevance cycle, emphasises the connection to an local environment including social and technological requirements. This cycle ensures that the designs are practical and applicable in real-world contexts. The rigor cycle connects the artefacts with the broader architectural knowledge base. By integrating all cycles, the DSR methodology enhances both the relevance and rigour, since constant evaluation is present throughout the design process of architectural artefacts.

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DSR Method and its application to the architecture domain.
Diagram based on Three Cycles Design Approach
Design Science Research, Hevner, et al. 2007

Diagram showing the important distinction in-between
artefact and meta-artefact in the field of architecture.
Image: Zara Pfeifer, 2023, Maquette: Atelier Fanelsa, 2022

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On-site rural library cataloguing available material resources. Image: Author, 2022

Upon our initial visit to the building, it was evident that the structure was about to collapse. The locals believed that demolition was the best course of action. However, we aimed to demonstrate an alternative approach: ‘With and Within,’ following Garutti (2021). We collected an on-site catalogue (Gasperoni, 2024) assembling a material palette from the existing building and surrounding bioregion (Sale, 1985) to identify available materials and local resources that could be used in the renovation process. To present the future ambition of the project, our studio organised an exhibition, encouraging support for renovation over demolition among the neighbours. We started the deconstruction and repair of the building, working on site every other week. Occasionally we stayed overnight experiencing the different atmosphere of the building and its surrounding garden.

Collaboration on Eye-Level

For larger works, we teamed up with local craftspeople. By being involved in the process, they gained an understanding of our approach. Working side-by-side, we established a trustful relationship and appreciation for their individual approaches and skills. The collaboration impacted the interest in the local community to learn new skills, encouraging more regenerative building practices. This helped us later, on other larger architectural projects. Nevertheless it was sometimes difficult to get skilled craftspeople for particular tasks, we had to execute specialised work ourselves—and thus ended up learning a lot. This experience enhanced the practice-based knowledge of our studio overall and we continued to working on site.

Bioregional Craft Resources. On-site collaboration and design. Image: Pfeifer, 2023

Geo-based Sourcing and Prototyping

The available bioregional resources are analyzed and mapped (Material Cultures ,2021). For ,Material Resources’ wood, sand, and gravel are still available in the north of Brandenburg. Production for bricks and clay have stoped the 19th century. Instead, new materials such as hemp have been introduced by local producers. In the case of fieldstone, an important material from which most foundations of older buildings were built, the craftsmanship and knowledge of processing has been almost completely lost.

To give an example in the process of developing lime plaster for the walls, we worked closely with lime experts who analysed samples from six local sand pits to produce various mixtures. Each mixture was prototyped on site, taking into account the specific composition and grain size of the sand from each pit. After numerous trial runs, where the strength and water resistance was also tested, we successfully developed the “Gerswalder Mix,” a blend that captures the authentic color and style of the region.

This mix contrasts to industrial lime plasters, which are mostly pre-mixed and homogenized, with additional cement to achieve a neutral appearance. This makes them universally applicable but lacking in character. Such industrial mixes typically require the addition of artificial colouring agents or need to be painted over to achieve a desired aesthetic. The ‘Gerswalder Mix’ maintains the natural beauty and unique qualities of local facades.

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Local Sand Pit. Image: Pfeifer, 2023

Natural Resources of the bioregion. Figure: Atelier Fanelisa, 2024

The Uckermark to the north of Berlin was shaped by glacial activity during the last Ice Age, resulting in a varied terrain of moraines, drumlins, and glacial valleys. Large forested areas cover significant portions of the Uckermark, including mixed deciduous and coniferous forests. The Uckermark is dotted with numerous lakes, ponds, and rivers. The region still contains several wetland areas, including marshes, bogs, and floodplain wetlands. Much of the Uckermark is characterised by agricultural landscapes, including fields, meadows, and pastures.

Workshops as Learning Environments

Lime Workshop Repair of the existing half-timbered structure, new interior plaster, and lime-based paint. Image: Author, 2022

The plastering of the half-timbered walls of the building was carried out within a workshop (Fanelso, 2024). The combination of knowledge transfer about lime plaster as a material, and the applied experience, communicated through direct instructions on mixing and plastering, generated interest among a wide range of people. Homeowners, craftspeople, students, and architects learned about the history, sourcing, and uses of regional lime. Together, we had an exchange on craftsmanship, building materials, and self-build techniques. In Gerswalde we continued consultations and engage in village development to share our expertise in bioregionalism, sustainability, and architectural building culture.

Bioregional Architecture Practice

Construction site images showing the new metal structure next to the existing one.
Image: Author, 2022

The existing, structurally compromised building was stabilised using an internal steel structure (Mommert, 2023), as the preservation of the original timber-framed facade and wooden structure was a priority. To plan the new structure in space, we used simple, hands-on tools like white strings to outline the possible new space, and later to determine the structural layout. The new steel framework then allowed for an internal glass facade. Additionally, the missing facade adjacent to the neighbouring property, which collapsed during the intervening years of neglect, was closed using either wood-cement panels for fire resistance or partly with clay bricks to maintain structural integrity and aesthetic continuity.

Inside the building, the ground floor, poured with a robust lime screed, serves as an open workshop for our architecture studio. The floor is insulated with cellular glass and sealed with pigmented sunflower oil. All interior walls are newly plastered with lime and finished with lime paint. A staircase furniture piece made of recycled wood panels done by visiting cabinet makers from Japan leads to the second floor. It houses a bathroom and two niches as sleeping alcoves. The wood for the alcoves was taken from the village forest after a storm tore down trees, and were prepared for further processing with a mobile sawmill. The deteriorated roof rafters are insulated with regional hemp fiber and hemp lime panels for effective thermal insulation.

By using salvaged and climate-positive building materials, the KURA project thus aims for a holistic regenerative practice (Mang, 2012) in the built environment. The close collaboration with local craftspeople strengthens the local economy and promotes social cohesion. Our goal is to make a positive contribution in our activities in rural areas, including through the conversion of KURA, and to promote bioregional architectural practices developments more broadly.

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Ground Floor Plan, Scale 1.200, Atelier Fanelisa, 2022

Upper Floor Plan, Scale 1.200, Atelier Fanelisa, 2022

Discussion & Conclusion

Axonometric Drawing, Atelier Fanelsa 2022

The DSR methodology emphasises iterative cycles of design and evaluation above all. Our reoccurring presence in the village and on the construction site provided the essential framework while allowing for iterative, on-site adjustments. This adaptable approach enabled precise responses to the building's condition and experiments. Engaging local craftspeople led to a mutually-beneficial learning process, enhancing our understanding of traditional techniques while introducing regenerative building materials such as clay, or wood. This collaborative approach integrated both traditional craftsmanship and contemporary construction techniques, resulting in a hybrid design ethos that is both innovative and rooted in local tradition. (Fanelsa, 2024) The project contributes to a growing body of knowledge on sustainable, region-specific architecture and shows the potential of bioregional practices to inform broader

Zara Pfeifer, 2023

architectural discourse and application. The use of geo-based and bio-based materials, such as hemp and lime, aligns with contemporary building practices in Europe (BC, 2024). The project shows a scalable model of bioregional architecture, by integrating locally sourced materials and engaging with the community directly in the construction process effectively preserving

Axonometric Drawing, Atelier Fanelisa 2022

and retrofitting existing architectural structures. By developing regional materials like the ‚Gerswalde Mix‘, this project provides replicable examples of material innovation grounded in specific regional context, offering an approach for practitioners to apply regenerative theories across architectural scales. This project calls for a new value system in the built environment by integrating regenerative principles into architectural practice and education, enabling human and natural systems to coexist.

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The site as an open space for continuous experimentation and intervention.
Image: Author, 2023

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